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Published in:

The Journal of Supercritical Fluids

Link to article, DOI:

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.supflu.2020.104897>

Publication date: 2020

Document version: Revised version submitted to the journal.

Citation (APA):

Nathia-Neves, G., Vardanega, R., Hatami, T., & Meireles, M. A. A. (2020). Process integration for recovering high added-value products from *Genipa americana* L.: Process optimization and economic evaluation. *The Journal of Supercritical Fluids*, 164, 104897.

**Process integration for recovering high added-value products
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economic evaluation**

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Abstract

This study was organized into three experimental steps. In the first step, SFE was used for the extraction of the fatty acid-rich extract from unripe genipap. The extract with the highest yield ($4.6 \pm 0.1\%$) and total fatty acid content (16.6 mg fatty acids / g) was obtained at 30 MPa and 333 K. In the second step, the kinetic behavior of the overall extraction curves was studied, and the data were accurately modeled using the potential of the hot sphere diffusion model. Finally, SFE was coupled to low-pressure solvent extraction (LPSE) to obtain a genipin-rich extract (71 mg /g) from the defatted solid or SFE coproduct. The processes developed in this study (SFE and SFE-LPSE) were also analyzed from an economic point of view. The results showed that by integrating the processes it is possible to reduce the COM from US\$ 86.83/kg to US\$ 11.18/kg of product.

Keywords: Supercritical fluid extraction, Process integration, Fatty acids, Natural blue colorant, Cost of manufacturing.

1. Introduction

Currently, industries in various market segments have increasingly sought to use sustainable processes to obtain their products. Sustainable processes are defined as those that aim to maximize production while minimizing environmental impact by maintaining a productive harmony between humans and nature, thus ensuring the well-being of present and future generations [1]. Supercritical fluid extraction (SFE) is a promising green technique for obtaining nonpolar compounds, such as fatty acids, essential oils, volatile compounds, and carotenoids, from several vegetable matrices [2]. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) is the main solvent used as a supercritical fluid because it is a safe solvent for food applications and has a low cost and high availability [3]. Upon reaching a supercritical state (304.25 K and 7.39 MPa), CO₂ acquires properties such as gas-like viscosity and diffusivity and liquid-like density that increase the solvation power of the solute, providing a solvent-free product [3, 4].

On the other hand, if the objective is to obtain compounds with polar characteristics, the use of liquid solvents such as water, which is an inexpensive, environmentally friendly, and safe solvent for food application [5], is recommended. Extraction with liquid solvents can occur using pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) or low-pressure solvent extraction (LPSE), according to the characteristics of the raw material and the compound to be extracted [6]. In a previous study, Náthia-Neves, Vardanega and Meireles [7] observed that the genipin colorant can be efficiently and economically extracted at 313 K and ambient pressure (0.1 MPa) using water as the solvent.

Previous studies carried out with several vegetable matrices in different countries show the efficiency of the integration of the productive chain in terms of obtaining high-quality and economically viable products [8-13]. The integration of SFE with other

techniques (PLE, LPSE, ultrasound, and supercritical antisolvent (SAS)) has already been studied to maximize the recovery of different compounds from the same raw material [14-18].

Unripe genipap (*Genipa americana* L.) is a little-known fruit that can potentially be explored in an integrated production chain. The main bioactive compound of this fruit is genipin, a powerful natural blue colorant with polar characteristics that, in addition to coloring, has antioxidant, anticancer and neuroprotective activity and acts against liver diseases [19]. However, this fruit is also a source of nonpolar compounds, such as fatty acids, whose extraction has not yet been explored. The discovery of new sources of these compounds, especially unsaturated fatty acids, is the objective of many researchers because these compounds, also known as essential fatty acids, are essential in the human diet; i.e., they cannot be synthesized by animals, including humans [20, 21]. These acids, in addition to being a reserve source in most organisms, play a variety of cellular functions, such as lowering cholesterol, enhancing brain health, lowering the risk of coronary and fatal heart disease, reducing inflammation and normalizing heart rate variability [22, 23].

The main goal of this study was to explore the extraction of the unripe genipap fruit. To the best of our knowledge, there are no studies on obtaining oil from this fruit and neither the use of the defatted unripe genipap to obtain genipin. Thus, to achieve this purpose, the extraction of fatty acids by SFE was experimentally optimized, and a mathematical model was adjusted. Finally, integration of the SFE-LPSE processes was performed to obtain the fatty acids by SFE in the first step and a genipin-rich extract by LPSE in the second step. An economic analysis of this proposal was also evaluated in terms of extraction yield, cost of manufacturing (COM), capital investment, operating costs and extracts productivity.

2. Material and Methods

2.1 Sample preparation

Unripe genipap fruits were obtained from the company Sítio do Belo (Parafbuna, São Paulo, Brazil) in November 2016. The fruits were dried in a freeze-dryer system (Liobras, model L 101, Sao Carlos, Brazil). The dried fruits were ground in a knife mill (Marconi, model MA-340, Piracicaba, Brazil), and the particle size distribution was determined in a vibratory system (Bertel, model 1868, Caieiras, Brazil) using sieves from 16-80 mesh (Tyler series, Wheeling, USA). The mean particle diameter (d_p) was determined according to the ASAE method [24]. The ground samples were packed in impermeable plastic bags and stored at 255 K until the extraction assays. The true density of the particles (ρ_r) was measured by pycnometry with helium gas at the Analytical Center of the Institute of Chemistry/UNICAMP (Campinas, Brazil). The apparent density of the bed (ρ_a) was calculated as the ratio of feed mass to the volume occupied by the sample in the extraction vessel. The total porosity of the bed (ϵ) was calculated as $\epsilon = 1 - (\rho_a/\rho_r)$. The raw material was also characterized using AOAC methods to determine the moisture content (method 920.151 [25]), ash content (method 923.03 [25]), protein content (method 970.22 [25]), and lipid content (method 963.15 [25]); the carbohydrate content was calculated by difference. The assays were performed in triplicate, and the results are expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation.

2.2 Chemicals

Carbon dioxide (purity > 99.8%), which was used as a solvent for SFE, was supplied by Gama Gases (São Paulo, Brazil). The n-hexane used for the Soxhlet extraction was obtained from Dinâmica (São Paulo, Brazil) and was of analytical grade.

The reagents and solvents used for the conversion of fatty acids to fatty acid methyl esters were sodium hydroxide, supplied by Synth (São Paulo, Brazil); sodium chloride, supplied by Ecibra (São Paulo, Brazil); and boron trifluoride-methanol solution, supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (São Paulo, Brazil), all of which were of analytical grade. The Supelco® FAME (fatty acid methyl ester) Mix C4-C24 used as the reference standard and methyl nonadecanoate (purity > 98.0%) used as an internal standard were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Darmstadt, Germany).

2.3 Oil extraction

2.3.1 Soxhlet extraction

The Soxhlet method was selected as the conventional extraction technique for comparison purposes. Soxhlet extraction was performed according to the protocol of the AOAC method (AOAC, 1997). Five grams of sample was wrapped in filter paper and inserted into the Soxhlet apparatus connected to a solvent flask containing 300 mL of hexane. After that, the system was heated to boiling. Reflux was continued for 6 h, and then the solvent was evaporated under vacuum (at 308 K) (Marconi, model MA120, Piracicaba, Brazil). The mass of extract was measured on an analytical balance (Bel, M214Ai, São Paulo, Brazil). The assays were performed in triplicate, and the results were expressed as the mean \pm standard deviation.

2.3.2 SFE

SFE experimental runs were carried out in a commercial SFE unit (Spe-ed 7071, Applied Separations, Allentown, USA) equipped with a cooling bath (Marconi, model MA184, São Paulo, Brazil), a pneumatic pump, an electric oven, an extraction vessel of 5 mL (Thar Designs, Pittsburgh, PA), a compressor (Shulz S/A, model MS 3, Santa

Catarina, Brazil), and a flow totalizer (LAO G0, São Paulo, Brazil), as shown in Figure 1.

For the experiments, the CO₂ was cooled to 268 K by a thermostatic bath (Marconi, model MA-184, Piracicaba, Brazil) before reaching the pump. The vessel was assembled into the oven, which was maintained at the preselected temperature. The temperature was measured by a thermocouple introduced into the outer wall of the extractor vessel (Pyrotec, TP100, Campinas, Brazil). CO₂ was pumped into the system until reaching the experimental pressure, and the pressure was maintained for 5 minutes as the static period. After that, the blocking valve (Autoclave Engineers, model 10 V2071, PA, USA) and micrometric valve (Autoclave Engineers, model 10 VRM2812, PA, USA) were opened and carefully adjusted to maintain the system pressure. The extraction was performed until an S/F ratio of 20 g CO₂/g genipap was reached. For each assay, 3.5 g (dry basis, d.b.) of raw material was placed in the 5-mL stainless-steel extraction vessel, and the CO₂ flow rate was kept constant at 2.5 ± 0.5 g/min. The total CO₂ mass was measured by means of the flow totalizer and vented to the ambient. The extracts were collected in glass flasks submerged in an ice bath, weighed in an analytical balance (Bel, model M214Ai, São Paulo, Brazil), and stored at 255 K for further analyses.

2.4 Overall extraction curves

The kinetics experiments were performed under the optimal conditions with respect to the highest global yield (X_0) (temperature = 333 ± 1 K and pressure = 30 ± 0.1 MPa). For each kinetic assay, 50 g (d.b.) of raw material was placed in a 300-mL stainless-steel extraction vessel, and the CO₂ flow rate was held constant at 5.6 ± 0.5 g/min. The extraction process was performed in the same commercial SFE instrument described in Section 2.3.2. A total extraction time of 400 minutes was adopted to ensure

that the diffusion-controlled period would be reached. These experiments were performed in duplicate.

2.5 HSD model

The HSD (hot sphere diffusion) model is based on several simplifying assumptions, namely, spherical single-size particles; no gradient of velocity, pressure, temperature, or solute concentration within the fluid; no sample shrinkage; and a constant diffusion coefficient of extract through particles. Using these hypotheses, the material balance across a particle in the extractor, based on Fick's first law, can be written as follows [26]:

$$\frac{\partial C}{\partial t} = \frac{D_e}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \left(r^2 \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} \right) \quad (1)$$

where C is the component concentration in the particle, r is the distance from the particle center, and D_e is the effective diffusion coefficient. As this partial differential equation (PDE) is second order with respect to r , boundary conditions at two points of the r axis are required:

$$at \ r = 0 \Rightarrow \frac{\partial C}{\partial r} = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$at \ r = R \Rightarrow C = C^* \quad (3)$$

where C^* is the equilibrium concentration of a component in the particle and R is the radius of the particle. The initial condition of the PDE is as follows:

$$at \ t = 0 \Rightarrow C = C_0 \quad (4)$$

where C_0 is the initial component concentration in the particle. An analytical solution of equation (1) results in [26]:

$$Yield = Yield_{max} \left(1 - \frac{6}{\pi^2} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^2} \exp \left(- \left(\frac{n\pi}{R} \right)^2 D_e t \right) \right) \quad (5)$$

where *Yield* is the extraction yield in terms of the mass of one specific component per mass of raw material (mg/g), *Yield_{max}* is the highest extraction yield (mg/g), and *n* is the counter index of the summation. *Yield_{max}* and *De* are the two adjustable parameters of this model that should be determined so that the differences between the model and experimental data, in terms of absolute error, can be minimized. In this study, a genetic algorithm [27], which is an efficient optimization technique, was employed for this purpose.

2.6 Integrated SFE and LPSE process

The SFE and LPSE integration was performed to obtain two products, an extract rich in fatty acids and an extract rich in genipin. The extract rich in fatty acids was obtained by SFE according to the parameters optimized in Section 2.4, using the following process conditions: temperature of 333 ± 0.1 K, pressure of 30 ± 1 MPa, and S/F of 16 g CO₂/g genipap. The oil obtained by the SFE process was analyzed in terms of fatty acids. After the SFE process, the defatted raw material was transferred to another instrument, where it was submitted to LPSE to obtain a genipin-rich extract. The LPSE was performed according to the parameters optimized by Náthia-Neves, Vardanega and Meireles [7] (temperature = 313 K, flow rate = 2 g / min, and S/F = 20 g water/g genipap (d.b)). The aqueous extract obtained by the LPSE process was analyzed in terms of genipin. For global yield determination in the LPSE process, a 5 mL aliquot of aqueous extract was evaporated in a vacuum oven (Tecnal, model TE-3951, Piracicaba, Brazil) at 373 K. Then, the global yield was calculated as the ratio of the total extract obtained from the extraction and the amount of raw material used on a dry basis. The assays were performed in duplicate.

2.7 Analytical methods

2.7.1 Fatty acid composition by gas chromatography (GC)

FAMEs (Fatty Acid Methyl Esters) were analyzed by gas chromatography (GC-FID) with flame ionization (Shimadzu, model CG17A, Kyoto, Japan) equipped with a fused-silica capillary column ZB-5 (Phenomenex Zebron ZB-5, 30 m × 0.25 mm i.d. × 0.25 μm, USA). The samples were converted to methyl esters by esterification, as described by Joseph and Ackman [28]. Chromatographic separation was carried out according to Pollierer, Dyckmans, Scheu, Haubert and Treseder [29] with some modification. The temperature program started at 343 K (1 min) and increased by 279 K per minute to 583 K (15 min). The split ratio was equal to 1:30. The injection temperature was 523 K, and helium (White Martins, 99.99%) was the carrier gas with a flow rate of 2.2 mL/min. The fatty acid methyl esters were identified by comparison with the **FAME Mix C4-C24 standards**. Quantification was performed by internal normalization using methyl nonadecanoate (1 mg/mL).

2.7.2 Genipin quantification by HPLC analysis

The aqueous extracts were analyzed by an HPLC-DAD (Waters, Alliance model E2695, Milford, USA) system. Genipin was separated according to the method described by Náthia-Neves [30] using water (A) and acetonitrile (B), both acidified with 0.1% formic acid, as the mobile phase, with the following gradient: 0 min, 99% A; 9 min, 75% A; 10 min, 99% A and 13 min, 99% A. The temperature and solvent flow rate used were 308 K and 1.5 mL/min, respectively.

2.8 Statistical analyses

The parameters were evaluated with a randomized full factorial design (2×5) with temperature (313 and 333 K) and pressure (15, 20, 25, 30 and 35 MPa) in duplicate, resulting in 20 experimental runs (Table 1). The influence of the parameters on global

yield (X_0) and palmitic, stearic, linoleic and linolenic acid contents were evaluated by analysis of variance (ANOVA) using Minitab 16® software (Minitab Inc., State College, PA, USA) with a 95% confidence level (p -value ≤ 0.05).

2.9 Economic evaluation

2.9.1 Process simulation model

The extraction of bioactive compounds from unripe genipap fruit using SFE and the integrated process SFE-LPSE were evaluated. The required mass and energy balances of the processes were estimated by the commercial simulator SuperPro Designer® version 8.5 (Intelligen Inc., Scotch Plains, USA). Two operational scenarios were simulated: Scenario I represents the SFE process carried out using only supercritical carbon dioxide (SC-CO₂) as extracting solvent producing a rich-fatty acid extract; Scenario II represents the integrated processes (SFE-LPSE) where SC-CO₂ was used as extracting solvent in the first step; and the residue from the first step was used as raw material in the second step using water as extracting solvent. This integrated processes results two products: a rich-fatty acid extract (SFE) and a genipin- rich aqueous extract (LPSE). The experimental data for SFE simulation were obtained from this present study and the data for LPSE were obtained from a previous work [7].

2.9.2 Economic simulation

Initially, the SFE of unripe genipap (scenario I) was simulated using 2×10 L vessels and the experimental data obtained in the kinetic study to verify the impact of the extraction time and S/F ratio on the process productivity and operating costs of the production of fatty acids-rich extract from unripe genipap. In the sequence, the process was scaled-up to 2×50 L vessels, because 10 L - 100 L is the recommended size to start SFE plants for processing raw materials which are not commodities and are farmed in

small quantities [31, 32], which is the case of genipap fruit. For the scenario II, the SFE-LPSE process was simulated using 2×50 L for the SFE step, and one 100 L vessel for the LPSE step. Tables S.1 - S.3 (Supplementary data) present the process conditions and input parameters used for the simulation of the both scenarios. The economic analysis evaluated the total capital investment, operating costs and productivity of the both scenarios.

The total capital investment refers to the fixed costs that are associated with the process and includes the direct fixed capital, working capital and startup costs. Direct fixed capital (DFC) represents the fixed assets of the project, such as plant and equipment and it is calculated as the sum of direct, indirect and miscellaneous costs that are associated with a plant's capital investment. By default, the DFC is calculated in the SuperPro simulator using cost correlations to estimate the purchase cost of all major equipment and cost factors with respect to purchase cost to generate estimates to all other cost factors. The working capital was calculated by multiplying the number of day covered by the corresponding unit cost per day. The number of the days considered to estimate the working capital was 30 days. Finally, the startup cost includes pre-opening, one-time expenditures incurred to prepare a new plant for operation and it was calculated by the simulator based on specific percentage (5%) of the DFC.

The annual operating cost (AOC) include costs related to the demand of a number of resources (raw materials, consumables, labor, heating/cooling utilities and power), as well as additional operating costs (waste treatment, facilities, transportation, selling costs, running royalties, etc). The cost of unripe genipap included the acquisition, transport and preparation costs. Supervisory and administrative costs as well as labor costs were estimated by the simulator considering the base salary as reference. Finally, the utilities cost is due to the energy consumption involved in the pressurization, heat exchanges,

evaporators, spray-dryer and the electricity consumed during the process. In this study, the cost of waste treatment was neglected because the solid generated in the extraction processes are free of contaminant solvent and, thus, can be used as raw materials to obtain other products.

The simulation was performed assuming that the process present the same performance as the experimental results obtained in laboratory scale if the operating parameters (S/F, temperature, pressure, bed density and porosity) are maintained constant in a given process time [33]. The annual operating time was considered as 7920 h per year, which corresponds to 330 days per year of continuous 24 h per day shifts. The number of operators needed to operate the productive plants was considered according to the plant size. Literature recommends 1 to 3 operators for vessels' capacities ranging from 5 L to 500 L [33]. The economic data used for the cost model are presented in Table S.2. Depreciation (10%) and maintenance of equipment (6%) rates were also taken into account [34].

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Raw material characterization

The proximate composition of unripe genipap fruit used in the SFE process is shown in Table 2. The high moisture content of the sample acts as a barrier to the diffusion of SC-CO₂ into the matrix as well as the diffusion of oil out of the matrix, which consequently reduces the SC-CO₂ sample contact [35]. The moisture content for efficient extraction may range from 3 to 24% depending on the raw material used [35]. Therefore, the water content of the unripe genipap fruit after freeze-drying was adequate for the SFE process. The ash, protein, lipid and carbohydrate contents observed in this study are consistent with those found in the literature, ranging from 2.8% to 10.1% for ash, from

1.5% to 10.0% for proteins, from 1.7% to 11.4% for lipids, and from 74% to 91% for carbohydrates [36-39].

3.2 Global yield (X_0) and fatty acid composition

The SFE yield from unripe genipap fruit for two isotherms (313 and 333 K) at five pressures (15, 20, 25, 30 and 35 MPa) are shown in Figure 2. Comparing these results with those obtained by Soxhlet extraction revealed that Soxhlet extraction had a higher X_0 ($8.0 \pm 0.6\%$). This could be explained by the interaction between solvent recycling and the solvent/solute ratio used in the Soxhlet extraction in addition to the solvent boiling temperature employed in the Soxhlet method, which enhances the solubility of most extractable compounds and provides a higher surface tension and viscosity than SC-CO₂ [40].

The analysis of variance (ANOVA, $\alpha = 0.05$) showed that the pressure (p-value < 0.001) and the interaction between pressure and temperature (p-value < 0.001) significantly influenced X_0 in the studied range. The increase in the operational pressure at a constant temperature resulted in enhancement of X_0 , which is mainly related to the increase in CO₂ density, ranging from 781.3 to 935.3 kg/m³ for 313 K and from 605.6 to 863.5 kg/m³ for 333 K (Table 1). The three highest yields of 4.3 ± 0.2 , 4.6 ± 0.2 and $4.6 \pm 0.1\%$ were achieved at densities of 935.3, 863.5 and 830.3 kg / m³, respectively. The two lowest yields of $2.5 \pm 0.1\%$ and $3.48 \pm 0.04\%$ were achieved at densities of 605.6 and 781.3 kg / m³, respectively.

These results are in agreement with a previous publication showing that the solubility of vegetable oils in SC-CO₂ increases with pressure due to enhancement of the solvent solvation power, which provides a higher and better permeability of the solvent into the solid matrix [41, 42]. The effect of temperature on X_0 is more complex. At a

constant temperature of 313 K, an increase in yield is observed for pressures ranging from 15 to 20 MPa, where the CO₂ density ranged from 781.3 to 840.6 kg/m³. However, at pressures higher than 25 MPa, an increase in the extraction temperature to 333 K promoted an increase in the X₀ even though there was a reduction in the CO₂ density (787.3 kg/m³). This behavior is called a crossover pressure and can be defined as the point at which the slope of the solubility versus temperature curve changes sign and the opposite effects of solute vapor pressure and solvent density on solubility compensate for each other [43]. That is, at pressures lower than the crossover pressure, the effect of the density of the CO₂ was more pronounced in the X₀, while at pressures above the crossover pressure, the effect of the vapor pressure with the temperature had a more significant effect than the reduction of the CO₂ density, consequently increasing the X₀. The crossover pressure observed in this study, at which the isotherms of different temperatures (313 and 333 K) intersect each other, was 23.5 MPa. A similar behavior was also reported in previous works for different solid matrices [44-46].

Table 3 shows the fatty acids identified in the extracts obtained by SFE under different conditions of pressure and temperature. The results were expressed in two different ways: as mg of fatty acid per gram of extract, which represents the concentration of fatty acids in the extract, and as mg of fatty acid per gram of raw material, which represents the amount of fatty acid extracted from the unripe genipap fruit. The fatty acids present in all samples were palmitic acid (ranging from 20 to 28 mg / g extract), stearic acid (ranging from 14 to 16 mg / g extract), linoleic acid (ranging from 147 to 310 mg / g extract), and linolenic acid (ranging from 34 to 52 mg / g extract). No significant differences in the profiles were observed; that is, in all the extracts, the same fatty acids were found. Similar observations by Benito-Román, Rodríguez-Perrino, Sanz, Melgosa and Beltrán [47] and dos Santos, de Aguiar, Viganó, Boeing, Visentainer and Martínez

[48] indicate that the process parameters of temperature and pressure do not affect the profile of the fatty acids.

The analysis of variance (ANOVA, $\alpha = 0.05$) showed that the pressure and temperature significantly influenced only the linoleic and linolenic acid contents in the studied range. The recovery of linoleic acid was significantly influenced by pressure (p-value < 0.001), temperature (p-value = 0.043) and the interaction between pressure and temperature (p-value = 0.005). The recovery of linolenic acid was significantly influenced by pressure (p-value = 0.006) and temperature (p-value = 0.079).

The highest amount of total fatty acids was observed when the extraction was performed at 333 K and 30 MPa and 35 MPa and resulted in 16.6 and 16.9 mg/g of genipap fruit, respectively. Linoleic acid was the major fatty acid found in the extract from unripe genipap fruit (approximately $76 \pm 1\%$), followed by linolenic acid ($13.3 \pm 0.2\%$), palmitic acid ($7.2 \pm 0.2\%$) and stearic acid ($6.6 \pm 0.6\%$). These results show that unripe genipap fruit can be used as a good source for obtaining a rich extract of unsaturated fatty acids, such as linoleic and linolenic acids, that are essential to maintaining the integrity of cell membranes, brain function, transmission of nerve impulses, hemoglobin synthesis and cell division [48-51]. As there was no difference in the X_0 or the composition of fatty acids extracted at 30 and 35 MPa at 333 K, it is suggested that extraction from unripe genipap can be carried out at a pressure of 30 MPa and a temperature of 333 K. Although extraction by the Soxhlet method provided a higher extract yield, the amount of fatty acids extracted was lower, which indicates the higher selectivity of SFE compared to Soxhlet.

To the best of our knowledge, no study on the extraction of unripe genipap fruit using SC-CO₂ has yet been reported in the scientific literature. Therefore, the findings of this article were exclusively compared with conventional extraction of ripeness genipap.

According to Costa, Ballus, Teixeira Filho and Godoy [52], the genipap pulp extract obtained by shaking presents the following fatty acid profile: palmitic ($2.73 \pm 0.01\%$), margaric ($20 \pm 3\%$), stearic ($0.66 \pm 0.01\%$), oleic ($3.7 \pm 0.1\%$), linoleic ($35 \pm 19\%$), linolenic ($26 \pm 16\%$), behenic ($2.27 \pm 0\%$), and lignoceric ($1.3 \pm 0.2\%$). Figueiredo, Maia, Holanda and Monteiro [38] studied the oil obtained from the seeds and the pulp of the ripe genipap fruit. The oil obtained from the seeds presented the following fatty acid profile: palmitic (10.29%), stearic (9.74%), oleic (19.48%), and linoleic (60.49%). The oil obtained from pulp presented the following fatty acid profile: capric (2.25%), lauric (2.25%), myristic (5.26%), palmitic (37.2%), stearic (5.36%), and oleic (25.65%). These differences among the fatty acid profiles found in this study and the profiles reported in the literature may be due to variations in the raw materials used for the extraction, which were the pulp and the seed in the studies mentioned above and the whole fruit without the peel in the present study. Furthermore, the ripeness stage of the fruit may play an important role in the fatty acid profile.

3.3 Kinetic extraction curves and modeling

The extraction of a solute from a solid raw material involves three different periods: constant extraction rate (CER), falling extraction rate (FER) and diffusion-controlled (DC) [53]. In this section, the extraction kinetics were analyzed at 333 K and 30 MPa to verify the behavior of the extractions of oil from unripe genipap as a function of extraction time and S/F (Figure 3).

Figure 3a shows classical kinetic curves for obtaining fatty acids using SC-CO₂ [40, 54]. The extraction yield increases rapidly up to the end of the CER period (34 minutes; 3% yield), and the mechanism of mass transfer was mainly controlled by convection in the fluid film around the milled particles. Afterwards, there was a reduction in the extraction rate until the end of the FER period (112 minutes and a yield of almost

5%), which corresponded to the transition period between convection and diffusional extraction. After this time, the extract yield was reduced to 6% after 400 minutes of extraction, which indicates a long diffusional period. The curves did not present the classical plateau during SC-CO₂ extraction, which suggests that either the whole extract content was not extracted from the raw material in 400 minutes or other compounds were extracted due to the long period of contact of the raw material with the solvent inside the bed. However, to reduce the operational time and costs, it is suggested that the extraction of the unripe genipap oil be interrupted at the 112 minutes of extraction (S/F = 16), since it was observed that increasing the yield is slow along the processing time, and therefore, it would be more advantageous to start a new batch than to continue with the same extraction. This is in agreement with some studies that report that it is preferable to work on the CER period, sometimes extending it to the FER period [54].

The different fatty acids identified showed similar behavior throughout the extraction time. The predominance of linoleic and linolenic acids for the assays studied herein was observed, where the maximum yields of these acids after 400 minutes of extraction were 25 (Figure 3d) and 4.5 mg / g RM (Figure 3e), respectively. The contents of stearic and palmitic acids were 1.3 (Figure 3c) and 2.5 mg / g RM (Figure 3b), respectively. According to Figure 3f, genipin was also extracted during SFE, although it has low affinity for CO₂. This can be explained by the prolonged effect of the high pressure and the extraction temperature, which may have promoted cell disruption and facilitated mass transfer of the other solutes to the solvent.

The adjustable parameters for the HSD model are presented in Table 4. It was found that using GA with a population size equal to 200 and a generation size equal to 400 can guarantee obtaining reliable $Yield_{max}$ and De. The counter index in equation (5) was considered large enough that the change in its function value was less than or equal

to 10^{-6} . Noticeably, the De value of each component changes throughout the extraction due to variation in the composition, and the reported De values in this table are just average values. According to Table 4, the diffusion coefficients of the components changed from $0.059 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ for stearic acid to $1.187 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ for linoleic acid; however, the diffusion coefficient of the extract is higher due to the availability of other undetermined components in the extract. The highest extraction yield was obtained for linoleic acid (26.8 mg/g raw material), followed by genipin (16.9 mg/g raw material). The maximum extraction yield for linolenic acid and stearic acid were of the same magnitude, i.e., 4.9 and 4.3 mg/g raw material, respectively, while palmitic acid had the lowest extraction yield of 3.0 mg/g raw material.

To evaluate the prediction capability of the HSD model graphically, comparisons between the models and experimental data are illustrated in Figure 3. The data points in this figure are the average of two runs, and the error bars indicate the corresponding standard deviation. The dashed lines of the HSD model, as shown in this figure, pass precisely through the experimental data points. The HSD model has better agreement with the experimental data at higher extraction times. This difference in accuracy can be attributed to the fact that the diffusion mass transfer mechanism, which was employed in this study, is more reliable for the later stages of extraction. However, the main mechanism in the early stages of extraction is the convection mass transfer between solid and supercritical fluid, which was ignored in the HSD model.

3.4 Process integration: obtaining fatty acids and genipin

Process integration for obtaining fatty acids and genipin-rich extracts was performed in two steps. In the first step, SFE was carried out under the optimized conditions selected in the first part of this study (Section 2.4), namely, a temperature, pressure, S/F and flow rate of $333 \pm 0.1 \text{ K}$, $30 \pm 1 \text{ MPa}$, 16, and $2.5 \pm 0.5 \text{ g/min}$,

respectively in order to obtaining fatty acids. In the second step, the defatted raw material was submitted to LPSE using water as the solvent for the recovery of genipin. According to a previous study by Náthia-Neves, Vardanega and Meireles [7], the optimum conditions for the LPSE process are a temperature, pressure, S/F, and solvent flow rate of 313 K, 0.1 MPa, and 2 g / min, respectively. Table 5 presents the results obtained in the integrated process. In the first step, a fatty acid-rich extract mainly composed of linoleic acid was obtained (10.9 ± 0.8 mg/g RM), which is an important unsaturated fatty acid that represents approximately 1% of the unripe genipap fruit. In the second step, LPSE allowed the recovery of 71 ± 6 mg / g RM of genipin (approximately 7% of unripe genipap). The purity of the extract obtained by LPSE was 115 ± 5 mg of genipin/g extract. The results obtained in this study are in agreement with those reported in the literature regarding the genipin content of unripe genipap fruit (1 to 9%) [37, 55]. Náthia-Neves, Vardanega and Meireles [7] recovered 80 ± 6 mg genipin / g RM using only the LPSE method. Thus, it can be concluded that the use of a defatted raw material does not alter the yield of genipin and that performing the SFE process prior to the extraction of genipin with water does not promote degradation of this compound. It is worth noting that the residue resulting from this integrated process has the potential to be used for the development of other products, for example natural encapsulating material and flour to be used in bakery products (cake and breads).

The integration of the SFE process with other techniques to obtain different products from the same raw material has already proved to be successful. For example, Moraes, Zobot and Meireles [14] studied the integration of SFE-LPSE to obtain bixin and tocotrienol-rich oil from annatto seeds; Osorio-Tobón, Carvalho, Rostagno, Petenate and Meireles [56] studied the integration of SFE-PLE-SAS to obtain volatile oil and powdered curcuminoid-rich extract from turmeric; and Cardenas-Toro, Forster-Carneiro, Rostagno,

Petenate, Maugeri Filho and Meireles [15] studied the integration of SFE-subcritical water hydrolysis to obtain carotenoids and sugars from pressed palm fiber.

3.5 Economic evaluation

The oil productivity and cost of manufacturing (COM) estimated for a 2×10 L scale are presented in Figure 4. The maximum productivity was observed at 30 min of extraction coinciding with region of the end of CER period (34 min) where was also observed the lowest COM (US\$ 281.41/kg). This is considered a typical behavior for SC-CO₂ extraction of bioactive compounds [31, 57, 58] because at the end of CER period the process presents the highest extraction rate with a better usage of the raw material [53]. However, for the extraction of fatty acid from genipap at the CER period only approximately 50% of the total extract was recovered, indicating that a great portion of fatty acids remain in the raw material, which is not technically feasible looking towards the further integration of the process to recover the genipin-rich fraction. Thus, despite the lowest COM obtained at the CER period, in this case it would be recommended to carry out the process up to reach the FER period, that presented a COM of US\$ 335.46/kg of extract.

In this sense, for the integrated process (Scenario II), the SFE step was carried out until the end of FER period and, thus, the LPSE step was carried out. Table 6 summarizes the total capital investment and operating costs as well as oil and genipap extract productivity for the both scenarios. Obviously, the highest investment cost was obtained for the Scenario II because the DFC is higher due to the necessity of adding the equipment required to operate the LPSE step, which correspond to a 100 L extraction vessel as well as, the equipment used to remove the solvent from the genipin-rich extract.

Regarding the AOC, it can be seen that for the SFE process (Scenario I) the main contribution is related to the raw material acquisition (65%), similarly to the observed for the extraction of other bioactive compounds using SFE technology, such as oleoresin from malagueta pepper [57], oil from pequi [58], oil from turmeric [59], among others. This behavior indicates that the operating costs of the SFE process is dependent of the amount of raw material required, which in turn is dependent of the number of batches performed per year. For Scenario II, although the AOC is higher than for Scenario I, the contribution of the raw material acquisition cost is lower than obtained in Scenario I. This is associated with the longer process time required to perform the both steps of the integrated process in Scenario II, which results a lower number of batches per year. Scenario II also presents a higher facility-dependent cost that represents the main contribution to its AOC and is due to the higher DFC required in this scenario.

However, considering the productivity obtained in each scenario at a 2×50 L scale, the AOC divided per the total amount of product obtained, a COM of US\$ 86.83/kg of product is observed for Scenario I and US\$ 11.18/kg of product for Scenario II, demonstrating that by integrating the SFE+LPSE, it would be possible to reduce the COM by 8 times due to the better usage of the raw material. This tendency has been also observed by other authors. Vardanega, Carvalho, Albarelli, Santos and Meireles [32] also observed that an integrated process resulted a lower AOC for the recovery of extracts with different compositions from Brazilian ginseng roots. By integrating SFE with the pressurized liquid extraction (PLE) to recover bioactive compounds from turmeric rhizomes it was possible to reduce 31.4% the COM of the turmeric essential oil [16].

To ensure if a certain process is economically feasible or not it is necessary to estimate the revenues of the project based on the selling price of the products. However, to establish selling prices for genipap products is a challenging task because there are not

similar products as reference in the market. Despite of this, by comparing the COM of the products obtained by SFE+LPSE in this study with COM of extracts obtained by SFE from other raw materials [59-61], it is evident that the reduction of the COM of genipap products as a function of the process integration can be a very feasible process.

4. Conclusion

The results of this study show that it is possible to obtain an extract rich in fatty acids, consisting mainly of linoleic acid (76%), from unripe genipap fruit. The optimum conditions for the fatty acid extraction were a temperature of 333 K and a pressure of 30 MP that extracted a total fatty acid content of 16.6 mg/g of unripe genipap. According to the HSD model, the highest extraction yields for the involved components ranged from 26.83 mg/g raw material for linoleic acid to 3.02 mg/g raw material for palmitic acid. The model also predicted that the diffusion coefficient for the components were between $0.059 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$ and $1.187 \times 10^{-13} \text{ m}^2/\text{s}$. Furthermore, the integration of SFE with LPSE allowed obtaining a fatty acid-rich extract and a genipin-rich extract, which are products of great industrial interest. The economic analysis performed showed that the proposal of this study is promising and can encourage industrial applications due to the better usage of the raw material. Since the COM was reduced by 8 times it can be concluded that process integration can be a very feasible process.

Acknowledgments

G. Náthia-Neves thanks CAPES - Coordination of Superior Level Staff Improvement - Brazil (Finance Code 001) for a Ph.D. assistantship. T. Hatami and Renata Vardanega thank CAPES (Finance Code 001) for a postdoctoral assistantship, and M. A. A. Meireles thanks CNPq for a productivity grant (302423/2015-0).

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Table 1. Experimental conditions studied in the SFE of genipap fruit and global yield (X_0) results.

Temperature (K)	Pressure (MPa)	CO ₂ density (kg/m ³)	X ₀ (%)
313 ± 0.1	15 ± 1	781.32	3.48 ± 0.04
	20 ± 1	840.61	3.7 ± 0.1
	25 ± 1	880.15	4 ± 0.1
	30 ± 1	910.47	4.2 ± 0.2
	35 ± 1	935.34	4.3 ± 0.2
333 ± 0.1	15 ± 1	605.60	2.5 ± 0.1
	20 ± 1	724.63	3.4 ± 0.2
	25 ± 1	787.28	4.1 ± 0.2
	30 ± 1	830.33	4.6 ± 0.1
	35 ± 1	863.49	4.6 ± 0.2

X₀ (%) = gram extract / 100 grams of genipap fruit on dry basis.

CO₂ density data extracted from Nist (<https://webbook.nist.gov/chemistry/fluid/>).

Table 2. Proximate composition (% w/w) of unripe genipap fruit on dry basis.

Parameter	Results	Units
Mean particle diameter	0.23 ± 0.03	mm
Real density	1.41 ± 0.01	g/cm^3
Moisture	5.1 ± 0.2	%
Ash	4.16 ± 0.04	%
Protein	7.1 ± 0.5	%
Lipids	8.0 ± 0.6	%
Carbohydrates	80.7	%

The results are the mean \pm standard deviation of experiments performed in triplicate.

Table 3. Fatty acid composition of unripe genipap fruit extracts obtained by SFE and Soxhlet on dry basis.

Fatty acids (mg /g extract)	Soxhlet	Pressure and temperature									
		15 MPa		20 MPa		25 MPa		30 MPa		35 MPa	
		313 K	333 K	313 K	333 K	313 K	333 K	313 K	333 K	313 K	333 K
Palmitic	8.4 ± 0.4	26 ± 1	20 ± 2	26 ± 2	23.4 ± 0.4	26 ± 2	26 ± 14	20 ± 2	24 ± 2	28 ± 2	26 ± 2
Stearic	4.5 ± 0.4	14.8 ± 0.8	14 ± 2	16 ± 2	13.6 ± 0.6	14 ± 2	14 ± 4	16 ± 2	14 ± 2	16 ± 2	16 ± 2
Linoleic	66 ± 3	145 ± 16	196 ± 20	292 ± 16	252 ± 2	192 ± 28	272 ± 74	304 ± 12	276 ± 20	310 ± 26	284 ± 6
Linolenic	10.5 ± 0.3	50 ± 2	34 ± 4	50 ± 2	43.8 ± 0.6	50 ± 4	46 ± 12	52 ± 2	48 ± 4	52 ± 4	50 ± 2
Total	88.9	237.5	264	384	332.8	282	358	392	362	406	366

Fatty acids (mg /g RM)	Soxhlet	Pressure and temperature									
		15 MPa		20 MPa		25 MPa		30 MPa		35 MPa	
		313 K	333 K	313 K	333 K	313 K	333 K	313 K	333 K	313 K	333 K
Palmitic	0.67 ± 0.03	0.88 ± 0.06	0.50 ± 0.02	0.98 ± 0.08	0.8 ± 0.1	0.9 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.2	0.9 ± 0.2	1.2 ± 0.2	1.04 ± 0.1	1.2 ± 0.1
Stearic	0.36 ± 0.03	0.50 ± 0.04	0.34 ± 0.04	0.6 ± 0.1	0.5 ± 0.1	0.54 ± 0.06	0.6 ± 0.2	0.4 ± 0.2	0.6 ± 0.1	0.60 ± 0.04	0.7 ± 0.1
Linoleic	5.3 ± 0.2	9.8 ± 0.8	4.8 ± 0.8	10.6 ± 0.8	9 ± 2	11 ± 1	13 ± 3	9.4 ± 0.8	13 ± 1	12 ± 2	12.8 ± 0.4
Linolenic	0.84 ± 0.03	1.7 ± 0.2	0.8 ± 0.1	1.8 ± 0.1	1.6 ± 0.2	1.8 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.6	1.6 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.2	2.0 ± 0.2	2.2 ± 0.1
Total	7.17	12.88	6.44	13.98	12.1	14.44	16.6	12.3	16.6	15.64	16.9

RM: raw material.

Table 4. The numerical values of the adjustable parameters of the HSD model.

Component	Yield _{max} (mg/g RM)	D _e (m ² /s) × 10 ¹³
Extract	60.29	1.891
Palmitic acid	3.02	0.675
Stearic acid	4.25	0.059
Linoleic acid	26.83	1.187
Linolenic acid	4.91	1.028
Genipin	16.88	0.558

RM: raw material.

Table 5. Process integrated to obtain fatty acid (SFE process) and genipin (LPSE process).

	SFE Process T = 333 K and P = 30 MPa	LPSE Process T = 313 K and P = 0.1 MPa
Fatty acid (mg/g RM)		
Palmitic acid	1.6 ± 0.1	-
Stearic acid	0.9 ± 0.1	-
Linoleic acid	10.9 ± 0.8	-
Linolenic acid	2.5 ± 0.2	-
Genipin content (mg /g RM)	2.2 ± 0.2	71 ± 6

RM: raw material.

Table 6: Capital investment, annual operating costs and annual extracts productivity.

	Scenario I (SFE)	Scenario II (SFE + LPSE)
<i>Total capital investment</i>	<i>US\$ 1,249,000.00</i>	<i>US\$ 3,215,000.00</i>
Direct fixed capital	US\$ 1,128,000.00	US\$ 3,001,000.00
Working capital	US\$ 64,000.00	US\$ 64,000.00
Startup cost	US\$ 56,000.00	US\$ 150,000.00
<i>Operating costs</i>	<i>US\$ 955,000.00</i>	<i>US\$ 1,364,000.00</i>
Raw materials	US\$ 602,000.00	US\$ 580,000.00
Labor	US\$ 79,000.00	US\$ 79,000.00
Facility	US\$ 248,000.00	US\$ 657,000.00
Utilities	US\$ 26,000.00	US\$ 49,000.00
<i>Productivity</i>		
Oil	10,998.1	10,953.2
Genipin extract		111,046.2

Figure captions

Figure 1. Diagram of the Spe-ed SFE unit.

Figure 2. Global yield isotherms from unripe genipap extraction in supercritical carbon dioxide. RM; Raw material; d.b: dry basis.

Figure 3. Comparison between the HSD model (dashed lines) and the experimental data (data points). a) Extraction yield; b) Palmitic acid; c) Stearic acid; d) Linoleic acid; e) Linolenic acid; f) Genipin. RM: raw material. All results are expressed on a dry basis.

Figure. 4. Oil yield, oil productivity and cost of manufacturing (COM) for scenario I.

Figure 1

List of equipment and instruments	
1	CO ₂ reservoir
2	Blocking valve
3	Cooling bath
4	CO ₂ pump
5	Air filter
6	Air compressor
7	Pressure gauge
8	Extraction vessel
9	Temperature controller
10	Micrometric valve
11	Flow meter
12	Flow totalizer
13	Extract collecting vessel

Figure 2

Figure 3

Figure 4

